

Authorship inequality and elite dominance in management and organizational research: A review of six decades

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Ideally, the academic publication process should be meritocratic, fair, and accessible to diverse groups of researchers. Yet, many scholarly disciplines are far from this ideal state. To investigate the extent and nature of authorship inequality in management and organizational research, we compared the 60-year publication trends of three closely related yet categorically distinct fields: Management (MNGT), Human Resource Management (HRM), and Industrial-Organizational Psychology (IOP). By examining over 60,000 publications across 42 top-tier journals, our study reveals a concerning upward trend in authorship inequalities over time, especially in the field of IOP. Employing a quantitative discovery approach, we evaluate the productivity of the most prolific authors within each field and journal. Our analysis based on publication data from these highly productive researchers exposes a pronounced dominance of a select group of individuals in IOP, as compared to MNGT and HRM. Furthermore, our findings demonstrate that (1) authorship inequality has been steadily rising in the last six decades across all fields, and it is reaching alarming levels that threaten the sustainability of academic careers in organizational research. Especially, IOP has been grappling with issues of inequality since its inception and continues to do so. To illustrate the gravity of the situation, it is worth noting that the present authorship disparity in IOP closely resembles the income inequality distribution in Angola, a nation plagued by poverty and corruption for many years. Moreover, our findings also indicate that (2) IOP journals allocate significantly more space to the most prolific authors than two other fields' journals, (3) the super-elite scholars of IOP do not only publish more articles on average than their counterparts in neighboring fields, but they also dominate journals to a greater extent, as we observe a

higher frequency of the same authors on the top-10 most productive list in IOP than in the other two fields, and (4) the most prolific IOP scholars are more conservative in their publication venue choices. These findings have significant implications for practice, theory, and policy design. The concentration of journal publications in the hands of a limited number of individuals also raises important questions about the fairness and inclusivity of the academic publishing system.